

The Effectiveness of the Local Security Policy and Sustainable Development of Rural Areas in the Kuyavian-Pomeranian Province in Poland

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Abstract

Local communities in many countries are working hard to improve the level of sustainable development. It is important to pursue an appropriate development policy at the local level, including security policy in order to eliminate social, economic, political and environmental threats. Considering the above, it can be concluded that the main objective of the article is to analyze the relationship between the effectiveness of the local security policy, reflected in the high sense of security of the inhabitants of rural areas in the Kuyavian-Pomeranian Province (territorial unit in Poland), and the level of achieving sustainable development goals by the districts inhabited by them. As a research method, we used a survey and conducted it in the Kuyavian-Pomeranian Province. From all the empirical material, only records concerning rural areas were selected. Then a synthetic measure was constructed from the total of the obtained results. It has shown that the analyzed districts represent an integrated measure of development significantly in the analysis. This means that within one administrative unit (province), the area of areas significantly varies with proving ground development. The analysis of the statistical correlation proves the lack of a statistically significant correlation between the effectiveness of the local security policy and the level of sustainable local development in the rural areas of the Kuyavian-Pomeranian Province. So far, no research has been carried out on the effectiveness of local security policy and the sustainable development of rural areas in the Kuyavian-Pomeranian Province. The conducted research is an analysis based on a wide range of towels influencing the sustainable development of the region.

Keywords: Sustainable Development, Rural Area, Local Security, Security Policy

Introduction

Many of the challenges facing the mankind, such as climate change, water scarcity, inequalities and hunger, can be solved not only at the global level (Walewicz, 2018, 2019; Gierszewski, Siemiakowski and Urbanek, 2020), promoting sustainable development, but, above all, at the local level. Local communities in a number of countries are working hard to improve the level of sustainable development. They are the decision-makers and catalysts of change that unite global goals with their own local ones. In the above context, it is important to conduct an appropriate development policy at the local level, including security policy.

Local security policy should strategically ensure the sustainable development of the local community, while eliminating social, economic, political and environmental threats.

Local security policy has two dimensions:

- a) actions of the state aimed at ensuring security, especially in the context of the subject - systemic (but also, as mentioned by some researchers: public security or social peace);
- b) political concepts of security, based on traditional political doctrines - implemented or to be implemented in accordance with the declarations of the winners or local elections (Siemiakowski and Tomaszewski, 2020, p. 29).

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We can distinguish other approaches to politics, not only in relation to local activities, so both politics and policy. Politics is sometimes reduced to pragmatic executive actions implemented by local government, mainly based on the guidelines of central authorities. Politics is then treated as a way of performing these tasks. It has been observed that "the concept of security policy covers, generally speaking, the activities of a given entity in some area in order to achieve previously adopted goals. This means that first, far-reaching goals had to be set by politics in a given, important area of operation" (Pokruszyński, 2011, p. 9). In the model approach, local policy is influenced by the concepts of state policy (strategies, programs), followed by financial resources for their implementation. In addition, politics in the region is important; it refers to cooperation programs between local governments in a given field, as well as development strategies of individual local governments, which are assumed to implement the electoral programme announced by election committees gaining power in a given local government (Siemiątkowski and Tomaszewski, 2020, p. 35). Local security policy should be carried out in coherence not only with central guidelines and indications, but in cooperation with residents (public consultations, cooperation with non-governmental organizations) and the economic environment.

Polish strategic documents, in line with international policy, specify that actions taken in the context of local security policy should be consistent with the principles of sustainable development. Sustainable socio-economic development is one of the most important challenges of the modern world. This concept was defined by the G. Brundtland World Commission for Environment and Development established in 1983. It defined sustainable development as one in which the needs of the present generation can be met without depriving of the ability to meet the needs of future generations. This development relates to environmental, economic and social aspects (World Commission on Environment and Development, 1987). There are several other definitions of sustainable development in the literature. The definition proposed by Polish researcher Barbara Piontek is: "sustainable growth is such a growth, the essence of which is to ensure lasting improvement in the quality of life of contemporary and future generations by shaping the right proportions between three types of capital: economic, human and natural" (Piontek, 2002, p. 27).

In Poland, the document "Strategy for responsible development" from 2017 states: "Responsible development is development in which the needs of the present generation can be met without diminishing the chances of future generations. It is important to properly shape the relationship between the competitiveness of the economy, care for the environment and the quality of life. Thus, responsible development relates to economic, social, environmental, territorial and institutional issues. This means socio-economic development in which the process of integrating political, economic and social activities takes place, while maintaining the natural balance" (Ministerstwo Rozwoju, 2017, p. 35). As noted in the document, local government is an important link in this development. It is possible to analyze the activities for local security in rural areas, which are the foundation for the sustainable and balanced development of the country. In Poland, the development of small and medium-sized towns, especially rural areas, is particularly important in the local area. These often struggle with security issues, which are undoubtedly weak points in sustainable development. They include:

- unemployment rate affecting the sense of economic security;
- access to education and childcare;
- access to health care, especially specialist;
- environmental protection, especially accessibility to landfills, sewage treatment plants, household sewage treatment plants;
- green areas and afforestation;
- access to public transport;
- access to services;
- social participation.

The main goal of the article is to analyze the relationship between the effectiveness of the local security policy, expressed in the high level and sense of security of the inhabitants of rural areas of the Kuyavian-Pomeranian Province – located in the central and northern part of Poland. The total population of the province in 2016 was 2,083,000. 1,239,000 people lived in cities, while 844,000 people inhabited rural areas. The province is divided into 23 districts – including four cities with district rights. These are, in turn, divided into smaller territorial units – communes (there are 144 of them – municipal, municipal-rural and rural ones). The paper identifies the level of achieving sustainable development goals by the specific districts. In addition, the specific objective was implemented, i.e. the ranking of rural districts in the Kuyavian-Pomeranian Province in terms of the degree of implementation of the sustainable development goals was created. It was prepared with the application of linear ordering methods. In order to identify the sense of security among the inhabitants of the Kuyavian-Pomeranian Province, we applied questionnaire studies conducted between November 2017 and February 2018. The sample was selected in a targeted random way. The study was carried out using the PAPI (Paper and Pencil Interview) questionnaire. Targeted sampling consisted in interviewing the inhabitants of 19 districts of the Kuyavian-Pomeranian Province, while its randomness stemmed from the character of the research - the respondents had to be

willing to provide answers. There were 4,400 participants of the study. They answered questions concerning economic, political and health security and evaluated the efficiency of services (police, fire service).

In the study, the following research questions were asked:

Q1: Do the rural districts of the Kuyavian-Pomeranian Province strive to implement the assumptions of the sustainable development strategy to an equal extent?

Q2: Does the effectiveness of the local security policy in the surveyed territorial units affect the implementation of sustainable development goals?

The research process requires the following hypotheses:

H1: The examined districts show significant differences in taxonomic distances between synthetic indicators of sustainable development.

H2: The level of sustainable development is strongly correlated with the level of effectiveness of the local security policy. Hypothesis number two formulated in this way has its substantive justification. Theoretically, there is a cause-and-effect relationship between the level of sustainable development and the level of safety. Security is a basic human need. Having satisfied it, we feel an urge to fulfil higher needs, such as sustainable development.

Theoretical Background

From the national and local perspective, when pursuing a sustainable development policy, the following principles should be taken into account:

- sustainable development (balance of economic and social goals related to environmental protection; a holistic view of economic, social and environmental issues);
- non-discrimination in political, social and economic life;
- solidarity (including solidarity within and between generations);
- cohesion (territorial, regional, regulatory);
- public good and a democratic state (GUS, 2010, p. 10).

There are numerous publications on the safety of the local community, also in relation to the Kuyavian-Pomeranian Province in Poland (Gierszewski, Siemiątkowski and Urbanek, 2020; Siemiątkowski and Tomaszewski, 2020; Siemiątkowski *et al.*, 2020). A lot of research was conducted on the role of local government in the process of local development (Akukwe, 1996). In the context of local development, it is important to effectively manage shared resources, which also include local security. It is worth searching for effective tools to influence both central authorities and, above all, local governments, in order to direct the entire public administration system to stimulate local communities to effectively use common resources (Ostrom, 2009; Hurynek and Kordonska, 2018).

Since sustainable development was defined in 1983, it has been the subject of numerous studies. Papers have been published on the possibilities and anomalies of introducing sustainable development in general (Cooper and Vargas, 2004; Littig and Grießler, 2005; Du Pisani, 2006; Polski, 2009; Elliot, 2012) and in the context of Poland (Parysek, 1995; Broł, 1998; Noworól, 2007; Senczy, 2013). There are also more specific studies concerning sustainable development, especially in the fields of economy and ecology (Marsden and Smith, 2005; Polski, 2009).

Due to the changing role of cities, more and more attention is paid to the issue whether cities can develop in accordance with the principles of sustainable development (Basiago, 1996; Newman, 1996; Satterthwaite, 2009; Menegat, 2016). Research focuses on their influence on human security in areas such as sustainable local development, human rights and environmental protection, which are components of human security. It is shown that cities can significantly contribute to the safety of people, and thus to local development, including the rural areas that surround them (Szpak, 2015; Satterthwaite, 2016).

Rural areas play a special role in the research on sustainable development. The specific subjects include sustainable development in rural areas is analyzed in terms of both human capital as a factor of rural development, education, health care, as well as social problems of renewable energy development in rural areas (Kapur, 2019). A lot of attention has been paid to the state's tasks within rural activities, examining various contexts of these activities, from technological development through comprehensive rural planning and cooperation with cities (Knaap and Chakraborty, 2007), to the sustainable development of rural tourism (McAreevey and McDonagh, 2011; Lane and Kastenholz, 2015). What is an important element is innovative management that can meet the challenges of sustainable development (Biermann, Kanie and Kim, 2017).

Another significant determinant of both the level of local security and sustainable development is the quality of life of the inhabitants of local communities. The higher the level of the quality of life, the greater the attachment to the place of residence (Jankowska, 2014). Differences in the quality of life, on the other hand, result in the emergence of migratory movements and the movement of the population (Jankowska, 2013).

Methods

Two types of methods were used in this study. First, a fragment of a wide-ranging survey conducted by the authors in the territory of the Kuyavian-Pomeranian Province located in central Poland was presented. From all the empirical material, only records concerning rural areas were selected. The number of observations obtained was $N = 1715$. A synthetic measure was constructed from all the results obtained.

For this purpose, linear ordering methods were used to assess the level of object differentiation using a closed set of statistical features (Grabiński, Wydymus and Zielaś, 1989). The adopted method was described, inter alia, in other studies by the authors (Siemiątkowski, 2017; Siemiątkowski *et al.*, 2019, 2020; Gierszewski, Siemiątkowski and Urbanek, 2020; Siemiątkowski and Marszałek-Kawa, 2020), so there is no need to discuss it in detail. It is only worth noting that the standardization of features was carried out based on model methods, assuming the existence of a model object in relation to which taxonomic distances of the examined objects were determined.

The synthetic measure was calculated using Hellwig's method according to the formula:

$$d_i = 1 - \frac{d_{i0}}{d_0}$$

where:

d_{i0} – Euclidean distance of the object x_i from the reference object x_0 ,

d_0 – the critical distance of a given unit from the pattern (Ostasiewicz, 1998).

The individual elements of the local security system assessed in the aforementioned empirical study were adopted as the features of the examined facilities (districts), assessment of the sense of security and the prospects of its changes.

The same method was used to create a ranking of rural districts in the Kuyavian-Pomeranian Province in terms of achieving sustainable development goals. The assessment of the degree of achievement of the sustainable development goals according to the methodology of the Main Statistical Office (*Główny Urząd Statystyczny - GUS*), consistent with the international methodology, consists of twenty-two groups of indicators. They fall into four main areas: social order, economic order, environmental order and institutional and political order. Almost 180 different types of measures have been defined in them, which help to track the progress of a territorial unit (a state or its part) in implementing the idea of sustainable development. These measures have been adopted in this study as the features of the examined objects (districts) when creating their ranking in terms of achieving the goals of sustainable development.

It is extremely difficult to compare this progress in aggregate terms, given the significant number of indicators. On the other hand, comparing territorial units by means of one or several selected indicators does not give an unambiguous answer to the question which provinces are faster and which are slower in implementing the sustainable development goals. In this case, the so-called multivariate analyses come in handy.

In order to carry out a taxonomic study of the progress in the implementation of the assumptions of sustainable development of districts in the Kuyavian-Pomeranian Province, 178 features of objects (districts) were determined on the basis of the Main Statistical Office data. It should be emphasized that the list of indicators taken into account in building the synthetic measure is limited by the assumptions of the sustainable development strategy themselves. This means that other features than those indicated in the statistics of the Main Statistical Office, compliant with the international guidelines on the goals of sustainable development, are not included here.

Table 1: The list of district features included in the process of building a synthetic measure

Order	Field	Indicator	Dimension	No
social	Demographic changes	Natural increase per 1,000 population	in total	X_1
		Balance of migration for the permanent	in total	X_2

		residence of people of working age per 10,000 working age population		
		Demographic dependency indicators	post-working age population per 100 working age population	X ₃
			the number of non-working age population per 100 persons of working age	X ₄
			post-working age population per 100 pre-working age population	X ₅
Public health	Infant deaths per 1,000 live births	in total	X ₆	
	Share of deaths by cause in the total deaths	cardiovascular disease	X ₇	
		cancer	X ₈	
		respiratory system diseases	X ₉	
Deaths of people aged up to 65 per 1,000 people at that age	in total	X ₁₀		
Poverty and living conditions	Share of people in households using environmental social assistance in the total population	in total	X ₁₁	
	Average monthly gross remuneration (business entities employing over nine people)	in total	X ₁₂	
	Average usable floor space per 1 person	in total	X ₁₃	
Education	Share of children covered by pre-school education in the total number of children aged three-five	in total	X ₁₄	
		in the countryside	X ₁₅	
	Indicators of the quality of education and the level of knowledge of students	passing the final exams in vocational upper secondary schools	X ₁₆	
		passing the final exams in general secondary schools	X ₁₇	
Access to the labor market	Share of the long-term unemployed (longer than one year) in the total number of registered unemployed	in total	X ₁₈	
	The number of the registered unemployed in relation to the number of people of working age (as of December 31)	unemployed - women	X ₁₉	
		unemployed people with higher education	X ₂₀	
	Job offers for disabled people per 1,000 disabled unemployed	in total	X ₂₁	
	Share of graduates (not working yet) in the total number of unemployed	in total	X ₂₂	
		graduates - women	X ₂₃	
	Registered unemployment rate	in total	X ₂₄	

economic	Consumption patterns	Number of passenger cars per 1,000 population	in total	X ₂₅
		Utilities consumption in households per year per capita	electric energy	X ₂₆
			gas	X ₂₇
			water	X ₂₈
	Income adequacy in old age	Share of long-term registered unemployed (longer than 1 year) aged 55-64 in total unemployed aged 55-64	in total	X ₂₉
		Share of people in retirement age in households using environmental social assistance in the total number of people of that age	in total	X ₃₀
	Determinants of health	Injured in accidents at work per 1,000 employees	in total	X ₃₁
		Outpatient clinics for 10 thousand. residents	in total	X ₃₂
	Criminality	The rate of detection of perpetrators of crimes identified by the Police	in total	X ₃₃
			in total	X ₃₄
		Crimes identified by the police in total per 1,000 inhabitants	criminal	X ₃₅
			economic	X ₃₆
			road	X ₃₇
			against life and health	X ₃₈
			against property	X ₃₉
	Road accidents	Victims of road accidents per 100,000 registered vehicles	wounded	X ₄₀
			fatal accidents	X ₄₁
	Economic development	Investment outlays in enterprises (current prices; excluding economic entities employing up to nine people) per one inhabitant of working age	per 1 inhabitant of working age	X ₄₂
		Entities of the national economy newly registered in REGON per 10,000 working age population	in total	X ₄₃
		Value of foreign capital of companies per capita of working age	in total	X ₄₄
Share of investment outlays according to Polish Classification of Activity in total investment outlays of enterprises (excluding economic entities employing up to nine people)		agriculture, forestry, hunting and fishing	X ₄₅	
		industry and construction	X ₄₆	
		trade; repair of motor vehicles; transport and warehouse management; accommodation and catering; information and communication	X ₄₇	
		financial and insurance activities; real estate market services	X ₄₈	
	other services	X ₄₉		

environmental	Employment	Natural persons running a business per 100 persons of working age	in total	X ₅₀	
		Entities of the national economy entered in the REGON register according to size classes per 10,000 inhabitants of working age	in total	X ₅₁	
			micro (up to 9 people)	X ₅₂	
			small (from 10 to 49 people)	X ₅₃	
			medium (from 50 to 249 people)	X ₅₄	
			large (over 250 people)	X ₅₅	
		Transport	Length of bicycle paths	per 10,000 km ²	X ₅₆
				per 10,000 residents	X ₅₇
			Length of local public roads per 100 km ²	hard surface	X ₅₈
				soil surface	X ₅₉
			Share of municipalities' expenditure on public roads in total expenditure	in total	X ₆₀
	Share of districts' expenditure on public roads in total expenditure	in total	X ₆₁		
	Climate change	Carbon emissions from plants especially noxious to air purity	in total	X ₆₂	
		Municipalities' expenditure on air and climate protection per capita	in total	X ₆₃	
	Energy	Electricity consumption per capita	in total	X ₆₄	
			in the city	X ₆₅	
			in the countryside	X ₆₆	
	Air protection	Air pollutants emission from plants especially noxious to air purity	gas	X ₆₇	
			dust	X ₆₈	
		Share of impurities retained or neutralized in pollution abatement equipment in plants especially noxious to air purity in general	gas (without CO ₂)	X ₆₉	
			dust	X ₇₀	
	Land use	Forest cover	in total	X ₇₁	
		Afforestation intensity	in total	X ₇₂	
	Biodiversity	Share of legally protected areas in the total area	in total	X ₇₃	
		Share of green areas in the total area	in total	X ₇₄	
	Waste management	Amount of mixed communal waste from households collected annually per person	in total	X ₇₅	
Share of communal and industrial sewage		in total	X ₇₆		

		subjected to treatment as percent of total amount of sewage requiring treatment		
		Number of household treatment plants	in total	X ₇₇
		Illegal dumping sites	number per 100 km ²	X ₇₈
area per 100 km ²	X ₇₉			
institutional and political	Openness and participation	Number of registered foundations, associations and social organizations per 10,000 residents	in total	X ₈₀
		Voter turnout in local elections	1st round	X ₈₁
			2nd round	X ₈₂
		Participation of women councilors and councilors with higher education in the legislative bodies of communes and districts	women	X ₈₃
	people with higher education		X ₈₄	
	Economic instruments	Proceeds to municipal budgets due to service charges per capita	in total	X ₈₅
		Funds from the European Union for financing EU programs and projects obtained by communes and districts per capita	in total	X ₈₆
		Expenditure from budgets of communes and districts for servicing public debt per PLN 1,000 in the total revenues of communes and districts budgets	in total (communes and districts together)	X ₈₇
		Share of investment expenditure of communes and districts in total expenditure	in total (communes and districts together)	X ₈₈
		Share of the area covered by the valid local spatial development plans in the total area	in total	X ₈₉

Additionally, it should be emphasized that the requirements of the adopted method impose certain rigours on the statistical features of objects. First of all, the data must be complete and collected according to the same methodology. Of the features meeting the above requirements, 35 were considered stimulants (X_{1t}, X_{12t}, X_{13t}, X_{14t}, X_{16t}, X_{17t}, X_{25t}, X_{32t}, X_{42t}, X_{43t}, X_{44t}, X_{45t}, X_{46t}, X_{47t}, X_{48t}, X_{49t}, X_{50t}, X_{51t}, X_{52t}, X_{53t}, X_{54t}, X_{55t}, X_{56t}, X_{57t}, X_{58t}, X_{59t}, X_{60t}, X_{71t}, X_{73t}, X_{77t}, X_{80t}, X_{83t}, X_{84t}, X_{88t}, X_{89t}) and 24 were identified as destimulants (X_{3t}, X_{4t}, X_{5t}, X_{7t}, X_{8t}, X_{9t}, X_{10t}, X_{11t}, X_{18t}, X_{19t}, X_{20t}, X_{22t}, X_{23t}, X_{24t}, X_{26t}, X_{28t}, X_{29t}, X_{30t}, X_{31t}, X_{64t}, X_{65t}, X_{75t}, X_{76t}, X_{87t}). The remaining features did not meet the rigorous methodological requirements of synthetic taxonomic measures. The features qualified for further procedure did not show an excessive degree of correlation with each other, and therefore they were all included in the synthetic index.

Finally, the degree of statistical correlation of the two integrated measures described above was checked. This procedure was to verify hypothesis number two.

Research Results

After carrying out appropriate procedures (including the selection of a pattern and the standardization of features), the values of a synthetic measure reflecting the effectiveness of the local security policy in rural areas in the province under study were calculated. This measure was calculated on the basis of the results of empirical research on the level of the sense of security of the inhabitants of districts in the Kuyavian-Pomeranian Province (see Figure 1).

Fig. 1: A synthetic measure of the effectiveness of the local security policy of residents in the rural districts of the Kuyavian-Pomeranian province

The ranking presented in Figure 1 shows significant taxonomic distances between the synthetic measures of security policy effectiveness across individual districts. The difference between the best and the weakest district in the value of the synthetic measure was as big as over 0.6, which means serious differences in the level of the perception of safety in the local environment and in the assessment of the elements of the local security system between individual districts. It also means that despite the fact that they belong to the same province, the inhabitants of its particular areas show significant differences in the assessment of the effectiveness of the local security policy.

The maximum value of the synthetic index reflecting the level of the sense of security and the assessment of individual elements of the local security system was over 0.6 (for the Mogilno district). This means that it was in the second quartile of the index distribution, which corresponds to a high level of local security. Two other districts were in a similar situation: Radziejowski and Brodnica. Nine districts obtained the value of the synthetic index between 0.25 and 0.5, which means the assessment of local safety at the level of poor. The remaining local government units (7) were in the last quartile of the distribution with the measure below 0.25 (= very poor level of local security).

It is worth emphasizing that the research on which the ranking was based was not fully representative. However, due to the collection of a significant amount of empirical material, it has a significant informative value.

Fig. 2: A taxonomic measure of sustainable development for rural districts of the Kuyavian-Pomeranian Province

The second conclusion concerns the level of sustainable development in the rural districts of the Kuyavian-Pomeranian Province. One can see a clear difference both in the ranking positions themselves and in the value of the synthetic measure. The maximum value of the synthetic index was approximately 0.3. This means that all the examined districts are below the second quartile of the distribution of the index values. This can be interpreted as a low or very low level of sustainability.

It is worth emphasizing that the ranking of the level of sustainable development was constructed on the basis of objective indicators (see Table 1). Therefore, it is not burdened with the subjective assessment of respondents, as was the case with the ranking of the effectiveness of local security policy. It can thus be concluded that from the objective point of view it is more credible. On the other hand, the presented comparison proves that the objective assessments of economic reality do not always coincide with subjective social perceptions.

The analysis of the correlation between the size of both synthetic measures brings interesting results. Pearson's correlation coefficient is only -0.27. In fact, this means that there is no statistically significant correlation between the effectiveness of the local security policy and sustainable local development in the rural areas of the Kuyavian-Pomeranian Province. A deeper analysis leads to the conclusion that some indicators taken into account in the process of constructing a synthetic measure of the local safety level are correlated to a slightly greater extent with the taxonomic measure of development. In all cases, the correlation is negative. It also does not mean a statistically significant relationship. In statistical terms, integrated local development in the districts of the Kuyavian-Pomeranian Province may be influenced by: strong attachment to the local community (correlation coefficient - 0.35), assessment of the sense of security (-0.34) and attachment to the place of residence (-0.34). However, the level of the correlation coefficient does not allow us to formulate unambiguous hypotheses in the discussed scope.

Summary

The use of a multidimensional taxonomic analysis to study the relationship between the effectiveness of local security policy and sustainable local development has undeniable advantages. First of all, it allows us to objectively show the differences between districts in terms of extremely complex, multifaceted issues. It shows these differences on the basis of a whole set of diverse characteristics rather than single parameters (e.g. growth rate). Thus, the multidimensional approach reflects the differences between the studied objects much more precisely.

The examined districts showed significant differences in the level of the integrated development measure. This means that within one administrative unit (province), there are areas that differ significantly in the level of sustainable development. Thus, the hypothesis number 1 was confirmed.

The analysis of the statistical correlation reveals the lack of a statistically significant correlation between the effectiveness of the local security policy and the level of sustainable local development in the rural areas of the Kuyavian-Pomeranian Province. A deeper analysis leads to the conclusion that some indicators taken into account in the process of constructing a synthetic measure of the local safety level are correlated to a slightly greater extent with the taxonomic measure of development. However, the low level of the correlation coefficient does not allow us to formulate unambiguous hypotheses in the discussed scope. Thus, hypothesis number two was rejected.

References

- Akukwe, F. N. (1996) *Community Development Cooperative and Democracy: A Guideline to Social Workers*. Nsukka: Veritas Printing and Publishing Co. Ltd.
- Basiago, A. D. (1996) 'The Search for the Sustainable City in 20th Century Urban Planning', *Environmentalist*, (16), pp. 135–155. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF01325104>.
- Biermann, F., Kanie, N. and Kim, R. E. (2017) 'Global Governance by Goal-Setting: the Novel Approach of the UN Sustainable Development Goals', *Environmental Sustainability*, (26), pp. 26–31. doi: 10.1016/j.cosust.2017.01.010.
- Brol, R. (1998) 'Zarządzanie rozwojem lokalnym. Definicje, cele, zasady i procedury', in Brol, R. (ed.) *Zarządzanie rozwojem lokalnym. Studium przypadków*. Wydawnictwo Akademii Ekonomicznej we Wrocławiu.
- Cooper, P. J. and Vargas, C. M. (2004) *Implementing Sustainable Development: From Global Policy to Local Action*. Rowman & Littlefield.
- Du Pisani, J. A. (2006) 'Sustainable Development – Historical Roots of the Concept', *Environmental Sciences*, 3(2), pp. 83–96. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1080/15693430600688831>.
- Elliot, J. A. (2012) *An Introduction to Sustainable Development*. Routledge.
- Gierszewski, J., Siemiątkowski, P. and Urbanek, A. (2020) 'Local Security in the Idea of Sustainable Development', *European Research Studies Journal*, XXIII(2), pp. 405–420. doi: 10.35808/ersj/1600.
- Grabiński, T., Wydymus, S. and Zielaś, A. (1989) *Metody taksonomii numerycznej w modelowaniu zjawisk społeczno-gospodarczych*. Warszawa: PWN.
- GUS (2010) *Wskaźniki zrównoważonego rozwoju Polski*.
- Hurynak, I. and Kordonska, A. (2018) 'Efficient Use of Common Resources in Conditions of Sustainable Development', *Torun International Studies*, 1(11), pp. 76–87. doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.12775/TIS.2018.007>.
- Jankowska, E. (2013) 'Directions of Foreign Migration of Poles and the Level of Socio-Economic Development of the Country of Emigration from the European Union Area in the Years 2004–2011', *Torun International Studies*, 1(6), pp. 33–42. doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.12775/TIS.2013.004>.
- Jankowska, E. (2014) 'Social Indicators and the Measure of the Quality of Life', *Torun International Studies*, 1(7), pp. 5–13. doi: 10.12775/TIS.2014.001.
- Kapur, R. (2019) 'Significance of Rural Development', *Acta Scientific Agriculture*, 3(7), pp. 167–173. doi: 10.31080/ASAG.2019.03.0538.
- Knaap, G. and Chakraborty, A. (2007) 'Comprehensive Planning for Sustainable Rural Development', *Journal of Regional Analysis and Policy*, 37(1), pp. 18–20.
- Lane, B. and Kastenholtz, E. (2015) 'Rural Tourism: the Evolution of Practice and Research Approaches – towards a New Generation Concept?', *Journal of Sustainable Tourism*, 23(8–9), pp. 1133–1156. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1080/09669582.2015.1083997>.

- Littig, B. and Grießler, E. (2005) 'Social Sustainability: a Catchword between Political Pragmatism and Social Theory', *International Journal of Sustainable Development*, 8(1–2), pp. 65–79. doi: 10.1504/IJSD.2005.007375.
- Marsden, T. and Smith, E. (2005) 'Ecological Entrepreneurship: Sustainable Development in Local Communities through Quality Food Production and Local Branding', (36).
- McAreavey, R. and McDonagh, J. (2011) 'Sustainable Rural Tourism: Lessons for Rural Development', *Sociologia Ruralis*, 51(2), pp. 175–194. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-9523.2010.00529.x>.
- Menegat, R. (2016) 'Participatory Democracy and Sustainable Development: Integrated Urban Environmental Management in Porto Alegre, Brazil', *Environment and Urbanization*, 14(2), pp. 181–206. doi: 10.1177/095624780201400215.
- Ministerstwo Rozwoju (2017) 'Strategia na rzecz odpowiedzialnego rozwoju do roku 2020 z perspektywą do roku 2030'. Departament Strategii Rozwoju.
- Newman, P. (1996) 'Reducing Automobile Dependence', *Environment and Urbanization*, 8(1), pp. 67–92. doi: 10.1177/095624789600800112.
- Noworól, A. (2007) *Planowanie rozwoju terytorialnego w skali regionalnej i lokalnej*. Wydawnictwo Uniwersytetu Jagiellońskiego.
- Ostasiewicz, W. (1998) *Statystyczne metody analizy danych*. Wrocław: Wydawnictwo Akademii Ekonomicznej we Wrocławiu.
- Ostrom, E. (2009) 'A General Framework for Analyzing Sustainability of Social-Ecological Systems', *Science*, 325(5939), pp. 419–422. doi: 10.1126/science.1172133.
- Parysek, J. (1995) 'Rola samorządu terytorialnego w rozwoju lokalnym', in Parysek, J. (ed.) *Rozwój lokalny: zagospodarowanie przestrzenne i nisze atrakcyjności gospodarczej*. Warszawa: Wydawnictwo KPZK PAN.
- Piontek, B. (2002) *Koncepcja rozwoju zrównoważonego i trwałego Polski*. Wydawnictwo Naukowe PWN.
- Pokruszyński, W. (2011) *Polityka, a strategia bezpieczeństwa*. Józefów: Wyższa Szkoła Gospodarki Regionalnej.
- Polski, J. (2009) 'Problemy kształtowania ładu przestrzennego w świetle idei zrównoważonego rozwoju', in Poskrobko, B. (ed.) *Wpływ idei zrównoważonego rozwoju na politykę państwa i regionów*. Wydawnictwo Wyższej Szkoły Ekonomicznej.
- Satterthwaite, D. (2009) 'The Implications of Population Growth and Urbanization for Climate Change', *Environment and Urbanization*, 21(2), pp. 545–567. doi: 10.1177/0956247809344361.
- Satterthwaite, D. (2016) 'Sustainable Cities or Cities that Contribute to Sustainable Development?':, *Urban Studies*, 34(10), pp. 1667–1691. doi: 10.1080/0042098975394.
- Senczy, D. (2013) 'Bezpieczeństwo ekologiczne a zrównoważony rozwój. Wzajemne relacje', *Przegląd Naukowo-Metodyczny. Edukacja dla Bezpieczeństwa*, (4).
- Siemiątkowski, P. (2017) 'External Financial Security of the European Union Member States outside the Eurozone', *Journal of International Studies*, 1(10), pp. 84–95. doi: 10.14254/2071-8330.2017/10-4/6.
- Siemiątkowski, P. et al. (2019) 'ASSESSMENT OF BASIC ELEMENTS OF THE SECURITY SYSTEM OF LOCAL COMMUNITIES', *Journal of Security and Sustainability Issues*, pp. 617–635. doi: 10.9770/jssi.2019.9.2(20).
- Siemiątkowski, P. et al. (2020) 'The Assessment of the Local Security Policy Efficiency', *European Research Studies Journal*, 23(3), pp. 217–237. doi: <https://doi.org/10.35808/ersj/1634>.
- Siemiątkowski, P. and Marszałek-Kawa, J. (2020) 'The implementation of the sustainable development goals at the local level. The case of the districts of Kuyavian-Pomeranian Province', *Baltic Journal of Economic Studies*, 6(2), pp. 1–8. doi: <https://doi.org/10.30525/2256-0742/2020-6-2-1-8>.

- Siemiątkowski, P. and Tomaszewski, P. (2020) *Lokalny wymiar polityki bezpieczeństwa*. Toruń: Wydawnictwo Naukowe UMK.
- Szpak, A. (2015) 'Cities and human security', *Torun International Studies*, 1(8), pp. 119–133. doi: 10.12775/TIS.2015.011.
- Walewicz, P. (2018) "'Greening" the Critical Theory of International Relations with the Concept of World-Ecology', *Torun International Studies*, 1(11), pp. 125–134. doi: <http://doi.org/10.12775/TIS.2019.003>.
- Walewicz, P. (2019) 'How International Relations Scholars Explain the World: a World-Ecological Critique', *Torun International Studies*, 1(12). doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.12775/TIS.2019.003>.
- World Commission on Environment and Development (1987) *Our Common Future: Report of the World Commission on the Environment and Development [Brundtland Report]*. 25, A/42/25. Oxford and New York: General Assembly United Nations.